

Evaluating Customer Trust in E-Commerce with a Combined Approach to Structural Equations and Artificial Neural Networks

Saeid Salam¹

¹ Department of Industrial Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Iran

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: 17 November 2020 Reviewed: 5 December 2020 Revised: 18 December 2020 Accept: 1 January 2021</p>	<p>Purpose: Due to the increasing familiarity of people with the Internet and considering the many benefits of online shopping, the fields of its use have grown rapidly. At such a stage, in case of mistrust among customers, this new phenomenon will fail in the first steps of progress. Organizing and supervising online stores is one of the essential indicators of e-commerce development, so that the electronic receipt and payment system for providing goods must be done in a safe and correct environment.</p> <p>Methodology: In this paper, various descriptive and inferential methods as well as neural network method for data analysis and PLS intelligent software are used to establish causal relationships of independent variables with dependent variables and MATLAB software is used to measure and predict dependent variables.</p> <p>Findings: The proposed model showed the priority and importance of key parameters and indicators affecting online trust.</p> <p>Originality/Value: The most important purpose of this study is to examine the dimensions and components of trust in the context of online shopping. Structural equations as well as neural networks have been used for this analysis.</p>
<p>Keywords: E-Trust, E-Commerce, Structural Modeling, Artificial Neural Networks</p>	

¹ Corresponding Author: saeid_salam19950@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

The access of a large number of people to the World Wide Web and the expansion of electronic communications between different individuals and organizations through the virtual world, has provided a suitable platform for establishing business and economic communications [1]. The rise of e-commerce has enabled people to make more and more transactions on the Internet. This brings us to a new business model that is impacting the global economy [2, 3]. At the same time, this type of business motivates the development of information technology and all economic sectors. E-commerce companies are creating a lot of online services and taking advantage of the opportunities offered by the Internet [4]. Online shopping, however, offers many opportunities for online shoppers, including convenience, choice, competitive prices, and a wealth of information. But in the meantime, there may be problems in making a purchase. You may not have access to the goods you have purchased or they may be defective and these and similar issues may not be resolved by contacting the seller. According to Turban et al. [5], there are limitations to the development of e-commerce, which are divided into two categories: technical and non-technical limitations [6]. These factors include the lack of standard technologies for secure payment and the lack of profitable business models, which play an important role in not meeting the expectations and predictions of e-commerce transactions in the Internet environment [7]. Therefore, due to the barriers to security and reliability in e-commerce, many e-commerce experts cite trust as a key factor in the success of e-business. Trust is the foundation of business, and is reduced through various means, including user uncertainty about the use of technology, lack of initial face-to-face interaction, and lack of attractiveness between the parties [8]. Virtual information security has always been emphasized as one of the basic infrastructures and requirements in the comprehensive development of e-commerce. Creating a level of security that is adequate to the needs and investment is possible in almost all environmental conditions. It is only by providing such a desirable level that individuals, organizations, private companies, and government agencies, while trusting and trusting the various parties that all participate in an electronic exchange and may never have seen or known each other, fulfill their expected role as Effective groups will play an interactive and synergistic network [9]. Given the above, the importance of customer trust in e-commerce is very important, so in this study we intend to propose a model to measure customer trust in this type of business.

2. Literature review

Trust is considered to be the most powerful relationship-based marketing tool. According to researchers, customers decide to buy online only on the basis of trust. In the traditional marketing literature, gaining the customer's trust is easily achieved if: the customer has a positive attitude towards trust, the customer already has a transaction and interaction with the seller, interacts with familiar sellers in this field, legal structure and be a strong supporter of the transaction and the customer hopes to establish a long-term relationship with the seller. However, many of the factors listed above are not readily available to customers and organizations on the web. In the traditional world, customer trust is affected by the seller's investments in buildings, facilities, and personnel. In the online environment, the customer faces an electronic store without a human factor and the low cost of entering and leaving the web environment has caused customers to consider the Internet environment and its sellers unreliable and unstable [10]. Jiang et al. [11] in a study, presented a model for calculating trust in e-commerce systems. To do this, it is necessary to be able to properly model the relationship between different fields. This modeling is based on ontological and hierarchical structures between different fields. The results show that the

proposed model has been able to improve the performance of current trust systems by about 70%. Mengjie [12] in a study investigated the relationship between factors affecting trust and education in e-commerce customers. The results of this study show that the differences in the factors affecting trust in different educational groups determine the relationship between people's education and knowledge of security methods and website trust. The more educated a person is, the security factors The Center considers trust and non-abuse of personal information more important than other factors, and in comparison with people with lower education, factors other than security, such as ease of use of the website, price and after-sales service are important and valuable. If comprehensive information on website security is taught to people with lower education, the factors that affect their level of trust in the website can change. Bekamiri et al. [13] in a study developed and validated a measurement model for e-commerce. The results show that trust is in fact a multidimensional concept. The proposed relationships within the trust structure show that website experience, innovation, and website quality are among the important variables in customer trust. Hoang and Nguyen [14] in a study examined customer trust in e-commerce in the United States, Singapore and China. The results show that the reputation and guarantee of the system from an online store is positively related to consumer trust. Customer trust has a positive relationship with their attitude and a negative relationship with perceived risk. The consequences of the results are discussed. In a study, Salameh et al. [15] examined trust in virtual communities and its effect on consumers' purchasing intent. The analysis shows that the ability of members significantly affects the three dimensions of trust in the online store in terms of ability, honesty, and benevolence. In addition, the ability of the store has a positive effect on the intention to obtain information and the intention to buy. In a study, Wang et al. [16] presented an integrated model using commitment-trust theory and the e-commerce success model in group purchases. The results showed that commitment, trust and satisfaction were the main factors on group purchase intention. Theoretical and practical concepts are also discussed in this research.

3. Research method

In the continuation of this research, the main variables of the research are identified and argued. The data needed to measure the above variables were collected by a questionnaire and in the field, then these data are converted into relevant scores and prepared for analysis using Smart PLS 2.0 software and MATLAB and SPSS. Since the researchers seek to use the results of the study in the short term and in the field of action (company), therefore, the present study is applied in terms of purpose. In terms of design, it is of descriptive-analytical type in which the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables is tried through a process including decision steps on the research problem or question or hypothesis, selection of research community and sample, determination of data collection methods and organization and analysis. Check the data. The statistical population of this study is an active e-commerce company. In terms of data collection, it is a field method that includes the collection of initial data or new information from the subjects themselves by methods such as observation, questionnaire, interview, etc.

In this study, because the number of statistical population was specific and limited and there was no difference in the selection of sample people and all people had the same chance to choose during sampling, so the simple random sampling method was used, i.e. no selection. There is no pre-existing mind and due to the limited number of community members, the sample members were determined using the Cochran's formula. N is the statistical population size, n is the statistical sample size, Z is the standard normal variable, which is equal to 1.96 at the confidence level of 0.95. P is the success rate, which is considered to be 0.5, and this is to estimate the maximum sample size, which is considered to

be more generalizable to the statistical results to the community. ε is the accuracy of the researcher (the amount of error considered), which is considered to be 0.05.

$$n = \frac{NZ^2p(1-p)}{N\varepsilon^2 + Z^2p(1-p)} = \frac{10790 * 1.96^2 * 0.5 * 0.5}{10790 * 0.05^2 + 1.96^2 * 0.5 * 0.5} = 371 \quad (1)$$

In general, data collection methods in a research can be divided into two categories: library and field. Library methods are used to collect information related to the literature and research background, and field methods are used to collect information to confirm or refute research hypotheses. Questionnaire is used as one of the most common tools for data collection in survey research and is a set of purposeful questions that use various scales to assess the views, perspectives and insights of a respondent [17].

In order to collect information for the literature of the present study from the library method (including reading books, articles, journals, conferences and internal and external conferences and research and study documents as well as performance reports) and to collect information needed to review and explain modeling and evaluation of trust. Customers in e-commerce with a combined approach of structural equations and artificial neural networks, field methods have been used. Field methods refer to the methods that the researcher has to collect information by referring to individuals, organizations, etc. and also establishing direct communication with them to collect the required information [18].

The research questionnaire consists of two parts: general and specific questions. The first part collects the demographic information of the respondents, which consists of 4 questions that are about: gender, age, level of education and income of the respondents to the questions. The second part of the questionnaire includes 32 questions that are related to research variables. After receiving the questionnaire, the proposed corrections were considered by experts so that the questionnaire has the necessary content validity. The validity of the structure was also calculated and confirmed using confirmatory factor analysis in Smart PLS software.

4. Analysis of data

In this paper, various descriptive and inferential methods as well as neural network method are used to analyze the data and smart PLS software is used to establish causal relationships of independent variables with dependent variables and MATLAB software is used to measure and predict dependent variables. The artificial neural network method is used. In general, the research steps are as follows:

Figure 1. Research process

In this section, to analyze the data, the method of structural equations based on variance is used to test the model hypotheses. Since the collected information is non-quantitative, in the first stage this information should be converted into quantitative information and in the next stage this information should be analyzed using statistical methods. In this chapter, along with inferential statistics, descriptive statistics of the data obtained from the questionnaire are presented and then data analysis based on inferential statistics and descriptive statistics is performed using appropriate statistical techniques to test the hypotheses. Given that each questionnaire was scored, the average score of the questions was used to answer the hypotheses. To test the conceptual model as well as the research hypotheses, structural equation modeling based on the least squares method has been used. Smart PLS software was used for this purpose. The conceptual model of the research is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of research

4.1. Conceptual model in Smart PLS

Structural equation modeling is a comprehensive statistical approach to test hypotheses about the relationships between observed variables and latent variables. Through this approach, we can test the acceptability of theoretical models in specific societies using correlation, non-experimental, experimental data.

The results of the structural equation model are presented in the form of a path diagram. A path diagram is a graphical representation of a structural equation model with three main components: rectangles, ellipses, and arrows. After presenting the initial model by structural equation model analysis software, one of the most controversial aspects of model modification. Modifying the model requires adapting a stated and estimated model by releasing parameters that have already been fixed or fixing parameters that were previously free. In this case, it removes the parameters that are not significant in the model and improves the model.

The following figure shows the conceptual model in Smart PLS software between the factors defined in the research. The conceptual model shows the relationships between variables whose correctness or inaccuracy has not been tested with experimental data.

Figure 3. Conceptual model in software

4.2. Structural model test in PLS

The validity and reliability of the external model estimates allow the evaluation of the internal path model estimates. The necessary criterion for measuring the structural model is the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the endogenous latent variables (latent dependent). China, the values of 0.67, 0.33 and 0.19 for the endogenous latent variables are described as significant, moderate and weak, respectively. 0 is acceptable, but if the latent endogenous variables are dependent on several exogenous variables, the value (R^2) should be at least at a remarkable level of 0.67 The coefficient values for the latent dependent variables of the study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination coefficient values

Hidden dependent variables	R^2
TO	0.952204

Here, from the bootstrap method of raw data, a value of T is obtained for each path coefficient between each of the hidden variables in the model. The analysis of these values is as follows: at the 90%, 95% and 99% confidence levels, this value with The Minimum T-statistics are comparable to 1.64, 1.96 and 2.58. That is, if the observed T value is greater than 1.96 with more than 0.95, it indicates the obtained relation related to the model.

Figure 4. Tested research model (value of t-coefficient of path coefficients and agent loads)

Fig. 4, shows the obvious and hidden variables as well as the path coefficients and factor loads. The numbers you see between the hidden variables of the model (variables shown in an oval shape) and the explicit variables (the variables in a rectangle that are hidden under the components of the variable) indicate the factor loads. The relationships defined between the hidden variables are the same as the research hypotheses, and the numbers shown on these relationships are path coefficients.

Investigation of research hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Investigating the tendency to trust customers' trust in online shopping.

Statistically, the first hypothesis can be expressed as follows:

H_0 : The tendency to trust does not have a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

H_1 : The tendency to trust has a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

Also for other research variables, H_1 hypothesis is as follows:

The tendency to distrust has a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

Online expertise has a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

Orientation and introduction have a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

The usefulness of information has a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

Brand strength has a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

Privacy and security have a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

Completing the order has a positive and significant effect on customers' trust in online shopping.

Table 2. Results from research hypotheses

		Path coefficient	T statistic	Result
BS -> OT	Brand strength -> Online Trust	0.121805	2.408257	Confirmation
OC -> OT	Order Completion -> Online Trust	0.131875	3.129226	Confirmation
OS -> OT	Online specialization -> Online Trust	0.175161	4.992578	Confirmation
OI -> OT	Orientation and Introduction -> Online Trust	0.182693	3.648176	Confirmation
PS -> OT	Privacy & Security -> Online Trust	0.189005	3.663302	Confirmation
TD -> OT	Tendency to distrust -> Online trust	0.127551	2.423972	Confirmation
TT -> OT	Tendency to trust -> Online trust	0.135918	2.765922	Confirmation
UI -> OT	Useful Information -> Online Trust	0.073657	1.575431	disapproval

As can be seen from the table 2, the path coefficient between the tendency to trust on customers' trust in online shopping is equal to 0.135918 and the amount of t-statistic is equal to 2.765922), So the assumption of a significant relationship between the tendency to trust and customer trust in online shopping is confirmed with 95% confidence. In addition, the path coefficient between the two variables has a positive sign. This means that with the increase and improvement of the tendency to trust, customers' trust in online shopping also increases.

Similarly, for other hypotheses, the results are specified in the table.

To date, the factors affecting customer trust in the online space have been identified, which are:

Tendency to trust, tendency to distrust, online expertise, orientation and introduction, brand strength, privacy and security, and order completion. In the next step, we use the design of artificial neural network to predict the level of trust of each buyer.

4.3. Predict online trust with neural network

The results of the questionnaire data are entered as neural network inputs and the trained neural network is used to predict the response variable (online trust). The study consisted of 10 neurons, including 7 inputs (28 questions related to the variables of tendency to trust, tendency to distrust, online expertise, orientation and introduction, brand strength, privacy and security, and order completion) and 1 output (4 questions). Related to online trust) is composed as follows:

Figure 5. Neural network error results

Due to the volume of input data (371 people), the neural network is well trained and also provides very accurate results. So that the error from the neural network is symmetric around zero and also the correlation between the actual online trust and the predicted online trust obtained from the neural network is approximately equal to 0.925.

Figure 6. Correlation between real online trust and predicted online trust from neural network

5. Result

One of the factors affecting the online trust of customers in the online store is the tendency to trust customers. This variable is one of the variables that is less in the dominance of the seller and the online store. In other words, this variable is less affected by the appearance features of the online store than other variables in purchasing from that website. This variable is largely personal, but it is possible to try to create a solution to consider your company as a supporter of the people and the community. In this way, the tendency to trust customers can be further stimulated.

Another factor influencing the level of customer trust in the specialized online store of customers is the issue of information technology and the field of Internet businesses. In order to increase the trust of customers by emphasizing their online expertise, it is possible to focus on training online businesses. For this reason, educational videos can be provided by the mentioned stores. These videos should be in an attractive and effective style, and at the same time try to open the positive points of internet business well to the public. Other measures that can be considered for this purpose are paying special attention to holding conferences in schools and educational centers for the new generation.

References

- [1] Salehi, F., Abdollahbeigi, B., & Sajjady, S. (2021). Factors affecting the trust in the online shopping and E-commerce Success of Companies. *Asian Research Journal of Current Science*, 1-5.
- [2] Nouri, F., & Ghahremani Nahr, J. (2019). Structural-interpretative Patterns of Factors Affecting the Sustainable Development of Agricultural Production Cooperatives (Case Study: East Azerbaijan Province). *Journal of Agricultural Economics and Development*, 33(3), 281-297.
- [3] Ghahremani Nahr, J., Pasandideh, S. H. R., & Niaki, S. T. A. (2020). A robust optimization approach for multi-objective, multi-product, multi-period, closed-loop green supply chain network designs under uncertainty and discount. *Journal of industrial and production engineering*, 37(1), 1-22. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681015.2017.1421591>
- [4] Aslam, W., Hussain, A., Farhat, K., & Arif, I. (2020). Underlying factors influencing consumers' trust and loyalty in E-commerce. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 8(2), 186-204. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2278533719887451>
- [5] Turban, E., King, D., Lee, J. K., Liang, T. P., & Turban, D. C. (2015). Business-to-business E-commerce. In *Electronic Commerce* (pp. 161-207). Springer, Cham. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10091-3_4
- [6] Aliahmadi, A., Sadeghi, M. E., Nozari, H., Jafari-Eskandari, M., & Najafi, S. E. (2015). Studying key factors to creating competitive advantage in science Park. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Management* (pp. 977-987). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-47241-5_82
- [7] Hoffman, D. L., Novak, T. P., & Peralta, M. (1999). Building consumer trust online. *Communications of the ACM*, 42(4), 80-85. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/299157.299175>
- [8] Juliana, J., Pramezwary, A., Patricia, V., Josephine, J., Lewinsky, S., & Putra, H. D. (2021). Understanding the Determinants of Hotel Consumer Trust: A Perspective Commitment-Trust Theory. *International Journal of Social and Management Studies*, 2(2), 114-121. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5555/ijosmas.v2i2.22>
- [9] Elyasi, M., Mohammadi, M., Baharloo, M., Khosropour, H., & Taheri, Z. (2021). Developing a Knowledge Managements Framework for identification of Success factors in the Product Acquisition Cycles-case of

- aviation Industries Organization. *International Journal of Innovation in Engineering*, 1(1), 76-100. doi: <https://doi.org/10.52547/ijie.1.1.72>
- [10] Nozari, H., Fallah, M., & Szmelter-Jarosz, A. (2021). A conceptual framework of green smart IoT-based supply chain management. *International Journal of Research in Industrial Engineering*, 10(1), 22-34. doi: 10.22105/riej.2021.274859.1189
- [11] Jiang, Y., & Lau, A. K. (2021). Roles of consumer trust and risks on continuance intention in the sharing economy: An empirical investigation. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 47, 101050. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2021.101050>
- [12] Mengjie, W. (2021). *Internet marketing and customer loyalty: Perfect Diary, as an example* (Doctoral dissertation).
- [13] Bekamiri, H., Ghasempour Ganji, S. F., Simonetti, B., & Seno, S. A. H. (2021). A New Model to Identify the Reliability and Trust of Internet Banking Users Using Fuzzy Theory and Data-Mining. *Mathematics*, 9(9), 916. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9090916>
- [14] Hoang, D. P., & Nguyen, N. H. (2020). The impact of corporate social responsibility and customer trust on the relationship between website information quality and customer loyalty in e-tailing context. *International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising*, 14(3), 215-235. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJIMA.2020.108715>
- [15] Salameh, A., Hatamleh, A., Azim, M., & Kanaan, A. (2020). Customer oriented determinants of e-CRM success factors. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 8(4), 713-720. doi: [10.5267/j.uscm.2020.8.001](https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2020.8.001)
- [16] Wang, W. T., Wang, Y. S., & Liu, E. R. (2016). The stickiness intention of group-buying websites: The integration of the commitment–trust theory and e-commerce success model. *Information & Management*, 53(5), 625-642. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2016.01.006>
- [17] Aliahmadi, A., Jafari-Eskandari, M., Mozafari, A., & Nozari, H. (2016). Comparing linear regression and artificial neural networks to forecast total productivity growth in Iran. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 8(1), 93.
- [18] Aliahmadi, A., Jafari-Eskandari, M., Mozafari, M., & Nozari, H. (2013). Comparing artificial neural networks and regression methods for predicting crude oil exports. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 5(2), 40-58.